

This paper is published at Journal of Int J Dev Biol.

DOI: 10.1387/ijdb.210073se

Hasanpour, S.

Eagderi, S.

Poorbagher, H.

[Hasanpour, M.](#)

[Maternal and zygotic activin signaling promotes adequate pattern and differentiation of mesoderm through regulation of pluripotency genes during zebrafish development](#)

To investigate the role of maternal Activin-like factors in the preservation of stemness and mesendoderm induction, their effects were promoted and inhibited using synthetic human Activin A or SB-505124 treatments, respectively, before the maternal to zygotic transition (MZT). To study the role of zygotic Activin-like factors, SB-505124 treatment was also used after the MZT. Promoting the signaling intensity of maternal Activin-like factors led to premature differentiation, loss of stemness, and no mesendoderm malformation, while its alleviation delayed the differentiation and caused various malformations. Inhibition of the zygotic Activin-like factors was associated with suppressing the *ndr1*, *ndr2*, *oct4* (*pou5f3*), *mycb* and *notail* transcription as well as differentiation retardation at the oblong stage, and a broad spectrum of anomalies in a dose-dependent manner. Together, promoting the signal intensity of maternal Activin-like factors drove development along with mesendodermal differentiation, while suppression of the maternal or zygotic ones maintained the pluripotent state and delayed differentiation.

Keywords: *ndr1*, differentiation, mesendoderm, zebrafish

[Mohammad Hasanpour](#) Contact Info:

✉ Dr.m.hpr@gmail.com

[Mohammad Hasanpour](#) Available at :

Google scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=IPyeGnYAAAAJ&hl=en>

Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=55696962500>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4109-0893>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mohammad-Hasanpour-9>

Web of Science: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/LVR-6050-2024>

SSRN: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/cf_dev/AbsByAuth.cfm?per_id=7241783

ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/me/uploads?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Bepress: <https://works.bepress.com/mohammad-hasanpour/>

Figshare: https://figshare.com/authors/Mohammad_Hasanpour/20360460